

**MERLIN Report: 3rd Hydropower Sector Roundtable on
Barrier removal within a Nature-based Solutions
(NbS) Approach**

Imprint

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MERLIN Executive Summary

For the hydropower sector the focus of these roundtable discussions is on understanding how the sector could contribute more to the removal of on-barriers (i.e. impoundments in river channels that hold back water) within an NbS approach. This may involve the removal of barriers linked to energy production, and/ or the removal of other types of barriers that, alongside other measures, helps the sector tackle socio-economic challenges by working with nature to support freshwater ecosystem recovery.

Nature-based Solutions (NbS) are “*actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems, which address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits*” (IUCN, 2020)¹. This is a different approach to thinking about and acting in relation to the natural environment – one that emphasizes the role of healthy ecosystems for sustaining and developing economic activities, for example energy production in the context of a changing climate. Mainstreaming an NbS approach across economic sectors, such as the hydropower sector, therefore holds the potential for the sector to contribute more to achieving the EU Green Deal.

NbS is an umbrella concept and thus there are many ways the sector could apply this way of thinking. In MERLIN we are focusing on one specific entry point – barrier removal within an NbS approach. Through a series of roundtable discussions involving those working within and with the sector, there are two overall objectives. The first is to identify key strategic actions to better support the sector to more widely adopt an NbS approach involving barrier removal. The second is to build a community of practice linking the economic sector representatives with MERLIN scientific and implementation partners to understand how Nature-based Solutions (NbS)² can be more widely adopted by the sector for tackling challenges experienced within sector, whilst also delivering benefits for people and nature more widely.

Following on from [the 1st](#) and [2nd](#) hydropower sector roundtables, the third **hydropower sector roundtable (RT3) was held on 14th May 2024**. This document provides a short summary of the 3rd MERLIN roundtable with the hydropower sector, presenting the main discussion points. This is a summary and does not involve a full analysis of all issues raised. Instead, this report focuses on new ideas and suggestions.

¹ IUCN 2020. Guidance for using the IUCN Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions: first edition. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN.

² Nature based solutions are not always adopted with the aim of restoring ecosystems. In MERLIN the focus is an NbS approach that contributes to freshwater ecosystem

restoration whilst also tackling different societal challenges (e.g. challenges experienced by the sector and/ or more widely). For the difference between this NbS approach and a traditional ecosystem restoration approach see [Ecosystem restoration and nature-based solutions: how do they differ and why does it matter? | The Freshwater Blog](#)

Content

- 1 MERLIN Hydropower Sector Roundtable Approach 5**
- 2 Example from Finland: Facilitating societal asset management within the NOUSU programme (Finland) – Assessing Net Present Value (NPV) with small hydropower operators 5**
 - 2.1 Why barrier removal?..... 5
 - 2.2 NOUSU programme and small hydropower 5
 - 2.3 Assessing Net Present Value (NPV) to inform decision making by small hydropower operators 6
- 3 Key themes identified from roundtable discussions 7**
 - 3.1 The strategic vision for barrier removal within an NbS approach for the hydropower sector..... 7
 - 3.2 Action A: Understanding barrier removal within an NbS approach 8
 - 3.3 Action B: Enhancing coherence between energy, climate change and biodiversity policies..... 8
 - 3.4 Action C: Developing clear finance pathways – aligning IUCN Nature-based solution criteria..... 9
 - 3.5 Action D: Co-developing sector tools to direct resources for greatest socio-environmental impact..... 10
 - 3.6 Action E: Strengthening public and private sector leadership and adaptive governance capacity 12
- 4 Next steps 13**

1 MERLIN Hydropower Sector Roundtable Approach

MERLIN's third Hydropower Sector Roundtable brought together 16 experts from the private sector (e.g. energy companies and their representative bodies), scientific research and non-governmental organisations. Discussions focused on further development of the strategic vision and the five strategic actions identified from discussions in the previous sector roundtables, alongside an ongoing desktop review of literature.

Prior to the roundtable the proposed vision and strategic actions were sent to participants to obtain written feedback to inform the planning of the third roundtable. This written feedback highlighted that overall, the five strategic actions identified were considered relevant and should be included in the strategy.

The roundtable commenced with a presentation by Antti Iho, an environmental economist and Research Director at the University of Eastern Finland. This provided an example of an economic decision support tool being applied within the Finnish Government's NUOSU programme, which provides funding for the removal of barriers to restore free flows in rivers and enhance conditions for migratory fish. Following this example, discussions were held to further explore and refine the strategic vision and the following five strategic actions that will form the core of the strategy for the hydropower sector.

1. Action A: Understanding barrier removal within an NbS approach
2. Action B: Enhancing coherence between energy, climate change and biodiversity policies
3. Action C: Developing clear finance pathways – aligning IUCN Nature-based solution criteria
4. Action D: Co-developing sector tools to direct resources for greatest socio-environmental impact
5. Action E: Strengthening public and private sector leadership and adaptive governance capacity

2 Example: Facilitating societal asset management within the NOUSU programme (Finland) – Assessing Net Present Value (NPV) with small hydropower operators

This example of a decision support tool in use in Finland was presented by Antti Iho, an environmental economist and Research Director at the University of Eastern Finland. This key messages from this presentation are summaries below.

2.1 Why barrier removal?

Rivers have always been a focus of human activity and are critical for human welfare. But there are different ways to use rivers, and the question is what is the best way to use them from the perspective of societal welfare? Some uses exclude others uses, for example hydropower and flood control barriers exclude other uses linked to free-flowing water. Thus, while all uses have benefits, there are trade-offs. We know the quality of river ecosystems has declined, and we have lost the fast-flowing sections of river (i.e. headwaters and the associated ecology) and lots of bedrock was removed, instead we now have long sections of standing water. We need to remove some barriers to reconfigure how we use rivers. Yet changing uses can be costly.

2.2 NOUSU programme and small hydropower

Finland has many barriers, including large sized hydropower dams. Around 100 of these generate about 97% of Finland's total hydropower production. Around 120 are business orientated but contribute very limited amounts of hydropower power and then there are around 500 barriers for which the contribution to overall hydropower production is unknown. These are often small hydropower facilities producing hydropower mainly for their own use (primarily for household use with excess sold to the grid). In Finland there aren't any 'obsolete barriers' as all barriers are performing a function. These barriers involving small hydropower operations are a primary focus for the NOUSU Programme that is aimed at improving the living conditions of migratory fish.

2.3 Assessing Net Present Value (NPV) to inform decision making by small hydropower operators

The focus for small hydropower facilities is to identify and work with operators who are coming to a crossroads in terms of the future economic viability of continuing operations. Decisions need to be made by these operators in the short-term about whether to invest further to comply with environmental regulations (e.g. create fish passes, install renew turbines) to continue to generate energy thereafter. An alternative decision is to retire the facility which provides opportunities to restore the river. Via the NOUSU programme operators can receive up to 50% of the finance to retire a facility. This decision is made by the operator. A calculator has been developed to aid this decision making by assessing the net present value (see <https://kalahavainnot.luke.fi/en/vesivoimalaskuri> and figure 1 below).

Figure 1: Assessing net present value calculator use to support delivery of NOUSU Programme

The focus is having discussions with owners of facilities coming to a crossroads. Many hydropower facilities may not yet be at this point in the economic lifecycle of facilities. Such small hydropower owners are identified by local groups (e.g. fishing associations), local government or NGO’s. The ecological value of removal is then assessed, following which the net present value tool is used jointly with the owner. This can be very quick (i.e. where it is clearly too expensive for the owner to consider removal) or it can be lengthy with the tool used multiple times. If option for removal remains (i.e. the owner may be in favour) then compensation needs to be agreed and a new/ temporary owner found to walk the facility through the removal process, including relicensing for removal. To date 4 small hydropower related barriers have been removed and 5 are being retired, 8 operators have engaged in the process but decided to maintain operations and 9 facilities are now under assessment.

Focusing on removing, where appropriate, small scale hydropower facilities can be considered ‘low hanging fruit’ in Finland to help restore free flows in river channels and tributaries. ‘Obsolete’ barriers are not found in Finland as there are always benefits arising from barriers in Finland.

3 Key themes identified from roundtable discussions

3.1 The strategic vision for barrier removal within an NbS approach for the hydropower sector

A vision provides a direction for steering change in the sector. This involves an overall goal for 2050, with objectives for 2030 and 2040. For this first iteration of the strategy being developed with MERLIN the focus is on achieving the objectives for 2030 to strengthen the conditions and develop clear action pathways for the sector.

Proposed Vision

Text provided before RT3

By 2030 the hydropower sector;

- Has embedded an NbS approach involving barrier removal as an explicit activity within company sustainability **strategies** across the sector and sector guidance.
- Provides financial resources for designing and delivering barrier removal within an NbS approach programmes.
- **Has helped create clear delivery pathways** at the MS and EU level to better organise barrier removal within an NbS approach at scale.
- Is contributing to learning and development of **human capital** within the sector for continued improvement/ refinement for how barrier removal within an NbS approach is viewed and applied.

By 2040 the hydropower sector;

- Is **celebrated** across Europe for its commitment to restoring freshwater ecosystems through barrier removal programmes that adopt an NbS approach and helps the EU implement the EU Nature Restoration Law.
- **Actively collaborates** with other relevant stakeholder groups (i.e. from different economic sectors, from the public sector and with the third sector) to design at scale barrier removal programmes through an NbS approach.
- Addressing challenges for the sector by working with nature **is considered the norm** for enhancing resilience and efficiency of hydropower assets of national strategic importance.

The overall goal of this strategy is that **by 2050** the hydropower sector **has made an active and significant contribution to the restoration of freshwater ecosystems** through on-line barrier removal and the co-development of multiple public and private socio-ecological benefits across different catchments, MS and regions of Europe.

Group discussion:

- The discussions focused on the scope of the strategy (which the vision needs to reflect). Some felt the scope could be broader (e.g. to include other types of NbS that sector could also apply, such as green roofs), whilst others felt the scope was broadly appropriate.
- There is therefore a need to clearly define the scope better in relation to the hydropower sector AND the types of barriers involved – which is all types of barriers (not only those linked to energy production).
- The aim is to understand how to open up opportunities to support the hydropower sector to address challenges, NOT reduce strategically important hydropower capacity (as a key component of the energy transition in some MS). Overall, therefore the focus is enabling greater exploration of ways to develop alternative configurations of barriers within rivers, with the sector contributing (alongside other sectors) to the removal of barriers that may not be fulfilling an economic role or have limited economic viability, designing and delivering such initiatives through an NbS approach.
- Such an NbS approach is important as it explicitly orientates initiatives towards addressing a range of socio-economic challenges for the sector (e.g. relating to perceptions of the sector or to address business risks linked to climate change impacts) with barrier removal as central but also complimented by other measures considered in the design stage.

3.2 Action A: Understanding barrier removal within an NbS approach

Summary text provided before RT3

Strategic Action A: Increase understanding of what an NbS approach for ecosystem restoration with barrier removal could and should entail with an explicit focus on benefits for the sector

Understanding of an NbS approach (i.e. as an alternative way of thinking about ecosystem restoration) and the idea of the hydropower sector undertaking barrier removal varies within the sector. The focus of this strategy is mainstreaming (i.e. increasing the uptake and depth of action within the sector) barrier removal within an NbS approach. To bring this about a shared understanding is critical of what barrier removal within an NbS approach entails.

An NbS approach is important as it frames ecosystem restoration by the sector as a positive opportunity (i.e. to help address sector challenges), whereas ecosystem restoration has traditionally been undertaken by the sector to comply with nature related regulations and policies. Adopting an explicit NbS approach in the sector could help action better compliment/ supplement strategically important hydropower operations. Whilst barrier removal often catalysis further ecological measures, an NbS approach explicitly focuses attention on designing to address sector challenges and deliver multiple socio-ecological and socio-economic benefits for hydropower operators, multiple publics and for nature (as loosely set out in figure 1). Removal of the physical structures of barrier is important but insufficient, instead an NbS approach positions physically removing the barrier structure as one (key) measure implemented in unison with other socio-ecological measures. Barrier removal within an NbS approach thus involves strategic planning at a catchment/ portfolio level.

There were two parallel group discussions with the aim of refining this strategic action further. In total 15 participants joined discussions to explore Action A further.

Group discussion:

- The definition of what is 'barrier removal involving an NbS approach' needs to be as specific and clear as possible. This is important as the strategy brings together two ideas (barrier removal *AND* NbS) that, on their own have started to gain traction across economic sectors, including within the hydropower sector.
- Illustrative examples could help (e.g. there is a large project underway within the Austrian Danube that has include barrier removal within some tributaries), as could an emphasis on the role of the IUCN NbS standards in assessing how well aligned an initiative is to an NbS approach.
- There is a need to distinguish between voluntary commitments and action (i.e. internally driven motivations) with action driven by external pressure to comply with legislation (although an overlap is both possible and desirable).
- There is a need to clearly set out the types of sector challenges that barrier removal within an NbS approach could help address, and the benefits that could arise for the sector, alongside other stakeholder and nature related benefits.

3.3 Action B: Enhancing coherence between energy, climate change and biodiversity policies

Summary text provided before RT3

Action B: Establish clear pathways within EU and MS policy for the hydropower sector to contribute to energy, climate change and biodiversity policy objectives

Multiple policy objectives are relevant to the hydropower sector (i.e. renewable energy, climate change and nature/ freshwater ecosystem restoration polices). The role of the sector, and thus what is expected, within policy is often unclear across EU and MS policy. Clearer pathways within policy can provide stronger signals to the sector (and those working with the sector) to increase the perceived relevance of such action within the sector, thus helping the sector better plan for the future.

At a MS level national strategic plans for the hydropower sector can help establish objectives for guiding more synergistic action by the sector and avoid local delays from prolonged deliberations on the principle of barrier removal by who and for what. For example, Sweden's National Plan for Modern Environmental Conditions for hydropower (NAP) (a box providing more information on Sweden's Hydropower and Environment National Action Plan will be provided in the final strategy). Environmental licence conditions (and time frames) for

hydropower barriers and their operation varies between MS. Many MS are reviewing (or planning to review) hydropower licences to strengthen ecological mitigation requirements to improve the conditions of rivers. Including specific requirements for the removal of barriers after hydropower operations have ceased could help strengthen the foundations for further action by the sector (i.e. that goes beyond merely compliance). Creating specific conditions for barrier after use can help the sector plan for the future and avoid hydropower barriers remaining in situ after operations have ceased. In addition, explicitly identifying barrier removal action as a relevant ecological mitigation measure (e.g. within or across catchments) could also help the idea of barrier removal gain more traction whilst aligning with the EU Sustainable Finance Taxonomy requirements for the sector. Licences can also however hinder implementation progress of barrier removal and other NbS related measures. Making barrier removal within an NbS approach by the sector more visible across policy could be beneficial by increasing the awareness of such action by decision makers within local government.

In total 7 participants joined this discussion about Action B.

Group discussion:

- Overall, policy needs to align to enable deeper/ broader recognition of the opportunities for the hydropower sector in adopting an NbS approach and undertaking NbS initiatives involving barrier removal as a key component. Otherwise, the positive outcomes from barrier removal within an NbS approach for the sector (e.g. to improve predictability and flexibility of operations for strategically important hydropower plants and thus achieving energy policy goals in the long term) may not be widely recognised and action by the sector to adopt an NbS approach and contribute to the removal of unnecessary/ unviable barriers will remain ad hoc.
- Policy coherence has been improving, for example with the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and the Nature Restoration Law, however challenges remain particularly in relation to implementation.
- Implementation challenges include an inconsistent approach to license reviews under the WFD.
- Licencing procedures need to support barrier removal as a core measure alongside others within an NbS approach and not be too lengthy or overcomplicated. Reviews need to be strategic (as opposed to ad hoc once licences cease).
- Reducing the complexity and length of licence procedures for the hydropower sector by linking to barrier removal initiatives could be an incentive for hydropower companies to incorporate such action more centrally into their core activities.
- Historic barriers may have cultural heritage designations (e.g. as found in the Debra River MERLIN case study in the Basque Country). It is possible to overcome possible policy trade-offs between barrier removal to restore free flows and heritage protection, e.g. by working with local government departments/ agencies and by undertaking partial removal.
- Impact assessment processes may be an important policy lever. Currently EU funding requires a more stringent assessment of ‘no significant harm’. Moving to a focus on net positive gain within impact assessments could strengthen business cases for barrier removal within an NbS approach as a viable mitigation option for some future some hydropower activities.
- In the plenary discussions the idea to create explicit links between an NbS approach involving barrier removal and requirements and metrics for hydropower companies within the EU Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive was also raised.

3.4 Action C: Developing clear finance pathways – aligning IUCN Nature-based solution criteria

Summary text provided before RT3

Action C: Developing clear finance pathways – aligning IUCN Nature-based solution criteria

The cost of barrier removal and associated ecological measures can hinder sector led action at scale, the ability to readily adopt an NbS approach involving barrier removal therefore varies considerably across the sector. Establishing clear finance pathways could provide stronger incentives (i.e. to inform cost benefit assessments by hydropower operators) to consider alternative/ additional actions as relevant and feasible by hydropower operators of varying sizes/ capacities.

There is a need therefore to establish a hydropower sector specific funding mechanism, for example that involves public and private finance sources complimenting/ supplementing one another. Public sector

resources could utilise existing public policy funding mechanisms. For example, the WFD cost recovery mechanism, which is underutilised within the hydropower sector. Furthermore, hydropower licence fees could feed into a common hydropower sector barrier removal fund.

The balance between public sector and private sector resources needs careful consideration as there are scale implications (the scale of action and the scale of engagement within the sector in such action). In Sweden there is a sector fund created and distributed by large hydropower companies, whereas in Finland a public sector funding mechanism (the NOUSU Programme) provides up to 50% of finance for supporting action across sectors to restore fish migration. Both these funding pathways (one drawing on private sector resources and administered by the sector themselves and the other drawing on public sector funds) have a strong focus on supporting action by small hydropower operators. Therefore, accessibility is an important consideration in the design of EU wide finance pathways for the sector. There is however also a need to develop a barrier removal finance pathway for the sector that encourages uptake and development of an NbS approach within the sector. Explicitly utilising the IUNC NbS criteria could help, providing a guide to help assess proposals for funds. For example, meaningful stakeholder engagement is critical for barrier removal and the need for inclusivity and public benefits is explicitly set out within the IUNC NbS criteria. Public sector finance could help support and / or be closely connected to such criteria, whereas other NbS criteria may be more closely aligned with private sector interests and needs, such as addressing sector challenges and the development of private benefits. Private sector funding mechanisms may draw on company specific resources and/ or other sources. It is however important that finance pathways for the sector do not reinforce a siloed approach, instead encouraging collaboration (i.e. between the public and private sector and across different economic sectors) is critical for supporting action at scale and for sharing learning (see action E).

In total 2 participants joined the discussion about strengthening finance pathways for the sector to support wider uptake of barrier removal from an NbS perspective.

Group discussion:

- The intersecting nature of public and private sector finance was emphasized drawing heavily on existing finance models across different MS, including in France, Sweden, Finland. In France for example, a tax has long been established to direct private finance generated through water use and administered by the public sector, to help maintain and restore freshwater ecosystems. This has to date supported the removal of numerous barriers. Thus, existing governance processes could be adapted to help leverage private sector resources to create a new finance mechanism for the sector, helping to reward good practice and incentivise further action.
- The different types of funding (private and public) need to complement each other, not as a hindrance. For example, some application of private sector finance could overlook some less visible barriers (or 'non-charismatic' barriers).
- In the plenary discussions, the usefulness of the EU Life fund as a finance instrument that works for large operators (providing 20% of the required finance) to support large dam removal projects was also emphasised.

3.5 Action D: Co-developing sector tools to direct resources for greatest socio-environmental impact

Summary text provided before RT3

Action D: Co-developing sector tools to direct resources for greatest socio-environmental impact

There is a lot of attention already on developing barrier removal tools, often involving a strong focus on migratory fish. An NbS approach to designing barrier removal programmes that seeks to incorporate wider biodiversity and associated socio-economic benefits could help unlock additional resources (finance, collaborations etc). To support the design of such action there is therefore a need for tools that help the sector consider a range of socio-environmental and business parameters to help understanding about what is feasible and desirable to achieve maximum socio-environmental long-term outcomes. Such tools need to be relevant, accessible and usable. Co-developing tools with the sector is critical to integrate sector needs and interest into their design. As well as informing the design stage of NbS with barrier removal programmes sector the develop and application of tools could also support more transparent decision making.

The following design principles could help guide the co-development process. 1. Assess cumulative impacts; 2. Systemic perspective (with multiple socio-environmental parameters (see bullets below); 3. Informed by evidence; 4. Adaptable (to update as conditions change); 5. Flexible (to incorporate different business targets).

Multiple socio-environmental parameters for consideration designing programmes

- Are there current uses/ economic function(s) of barriers? What?
- Are there any legal licences linked to these functions?
- Are there any environmental conditions attached to licences (what and how long)?
- Do local people/ communities have an emotional attachment to the barrier?
- Are there activities linked to the barrier that can support health and wellbeing outcomes for local communities?
- Are there any cultural heritage values?
- Does the barrier help or hinder the regulation of flood risk and water quality for communities in the catchment?
- Does the structural aspects of the barrier contribute to greenhouse gas emissions (i.e. from sedimentation and anoxic conditions)?
- Does the barrier trap sediment? Is sediment removed/ managed?
- Does the barrier reduce or exacerbate flood risk, water quality and water availability sector challenges within the catchment?
- Are there migratory fish within the catchment and what is the impact of the barrier?
- Does the barrier influence the distribution and health of local fish populations? How?
- Are there any notable freshwater ecological characteristics/ features (along river corridors and in the floodplain)?
- Are there any legally protected species and habitats in the catchment linked to freshwater ecosystems?
- Are there legally protected conservation sites in the catchment?
- Who owns the barrier?
- How accessible is the barrier for machinery?
- What is the estimated cost of removing a barrier?
- What is the condition of the barrier? Are there any concerns relating to structural integrity?
- What is the actual or potential for the barrier to enhance energy security locally? Nationally?
- How will climate change influence conditions in the catchment in the future?

In total 5 participants joined the discussion about tools to assess at a catchment scale where action (involving the removal of barriers alongside other measures) could be economically feasible and while maximising synergistic outcomes for the hydropower sector and for restored freshwater ecosystems.

Group discussion:

- Barriers and their geographies vary (i.e. context matters – a one size fits all approach is not suitable). Tools are needed to guide design, and delivery of catchment scale programmes that achieve win-wins for the sector and for nature. What is required are ways to understand future scenarios in terms of maximising different policy goals (i.e. the aim of tools should be the analysis of scenarios by considering multiple factors and policy goals).
- ‘Obsolete’ (as a key biodiversity policy focus) is a contested term, instead tools are needed to identify opportunities (based on multiple factors) and to guide how initiatives are designed (i.e. what outcomes are desired).
- Quick wins are likely to be found in relation to barriers not currently linked to economic activities, in supporting operators wishing to cease small scale hydropower activities (i.e. as highlighted by Antti Iho from the University of East Finland), and by incorporating upstream and downstream enhancements into programmes to achieve benefits for companies, local people and nature.

NOTE: Tools to understand scenarios need to not just focus on barriers but also support an NbS way of thinking to inform design of initiatives. For the hydropower sector this requires identifying sector challenges and connecting these (i.e. not just in terms of policy goals but also operational challenges) to multiple different measures (including but not restricted to barrier removal) to help the sector explore and better understand how working with nature could help the sector address challenges (e.g. a catalogue of examples).

3.6 Action E: Strengthening public and private sector leadership and adaptive governance capacity

Summary text provided before RT3

Action E: Strengthening public and private sector leadership and adaptive governance capacity

Developing barrier removal programmes within an NbS approach (i.e. upscaling action by the sector) has the potential to deliver greater socio-environmental benefits but involves even more complexity, e.g. to involve a greater range of stakeholders, perspectives and organisational levels, thus leadership capacity of different actors is critical to support and strengthen. The roles of different actors adopt to led and guiding in achieving barrier removal and in adopting an NbS approach will vary settings. In some circumstances the sector may actively support and help enable action, whereas in other settings leadership will need to come from within the sector. Leadership therefore needs to encompass the ability to understand potential for and to develop strategic partnerships within and beyond the sector.

In the sector multi-level leadership capacity is important. This involves strategic, high-level leadership for developing links to existing sector wide sustainability standards and guidelines. Within businesses high level leadership is also important for initiating a focus within companies on developing programmes and for ensuring resources are made available to do this in practice. Leadership is also needed to in the design of programmes to explore opportunities and identify priorities. Lastly, leadership to guide action on the ground is also important to deliver activities and measures to ensure the desired outcomes are achieved over time) and working with stakeholders to overcome unforeseen challenges and recognise opportunities.

The public sector has an important support role for developing sector led action. At a strategic level the public sector can help upscale action by bringing different stakeholders together by developing and guiding multi-stakeholder (i.e. across sectors) deliberative processes for exploring potential partnership opportunities to inform the design of barrier removal programmes within an NbS approach. The public sector also has a strong interest in the quality and quantity of public benefits that could/ should arise. Furthermore, many factors are known to be important in barrier removal with the potential to hinder progress if not adequately recognised and tackled. These factors include local emotional attachment to barriers, heritage designations, and unclear ownership of barriers. Public sector stakeholders (i.e. local administration) often have more expertise for navigating these factors and hence can provide important support to help sector led action move from design to implementation. This public sector support role is particularly important for developing action by small and medium sized hydropower operators who may have less internal capacity.

Public and private sector stakeholder also need to work together to co-lead the continued development and refinement of further strategic actions to encourage broader and deeper uptake of an NbS way of thinking and doing involving barrier removal. This includes forging stronger connections between existing sustainability standards and practices to the idea of barrier removal as an opportunity for the sector and broader NbS approach. Also, there is a need for sectoral metrics for the sector to demonstrate the impact of their action internally and more broadly.

There were two parallel group discussions, involving 15 participants, aimed at refining this strategic action further.

Group discussion:

- Leadership capacity of local public sector entities (nature protection and/ or water authorities) who are responsible for coordinating the implementation of WFD and the new nature restoration law regulations is needed for barrier removal within an NbS approach to be considered relevant at the MS level for addressing compliance challenges by the sector.
- However, an NbS approach can also involve action driven by other challenges (not just the need to comply). Thus, leadership from within the hydropower sector is also needed.

Key areas in the design and delivery of initiatives where public sector leadership is needed are;

- Strategic leadership is needed to convene multistakeholder deliberations for scoping barriers at the catchment scale, to administer funds and to strengthen public policies (national strategies) to better support action by the sector.
- Removal of barriers also involves transfer of land ownership and if public benefits are being provided then ownership should be transferred to the public sector.

- Permitting and licences for activities with benefits for nature and people (i.e. permitting for NbS initiatives), which can be a complex, lengthy process and thus a possible hinderance to action.

Private sector leadership to support more widespread uptake of NbS with barrier removal could include:

- Initial leadership could be provided by working with established industry networks/ associations within the hydropower sector (e.g. Eurelectric and the International Hydropower Association). Understanding the conditions for such entities to take on an ambassador type role and refine the ideas outlined in the hydropower strategy developed in this MERLIN project would be important. For example, to include voluntary commitments explicitly orientated towards barrier removal within an NbS approach into their plans and policies and to promote this more within the sector.
- Develop an EU Hydropower Standard (working with the Hydropower Sustainability Alliance) that explicitly goes beyond existing (well developed) EU legislative standards to also encompass how and why an NbS approach (including NbS initiatives with barrier removal as a core measure) could be applied by hydropower companies in Europe.
- It could be helpful to better understand why companies would/ would not voluntarily develop barrier removal and NbS programmes.
- Mechanisms could also be developed to harness the data, information and knowledge within hydropower companies to improve catchment scale tools and scenario analysis, particularly in relation to understanding economic lifecycles of barriers and sector challenges that could be tackled through an NbS approach.
- Better understand how to develop the capacity of the hydropower sector workforce to design and deliver NbS programmes with barrier removal.

Note: An NbS approach is a different way of thinking (about ecosystem restoration) and working with others (i.e. in partnership) from more traditional approaches to ecosystem restoration often embedded within public sector entities who have traditional led initiatives in the past. Ecosystem restoration has also often been traditional viewed narrowly within the sector in terms of a compliance issue, and as an operational threat. Leadership needs to reflect, reinforce and refine (when needed) an NbS approach as a fundamentally different way of working within both the public and private sector to support meaningful collaboration.

4 Next steps

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- A second draft of the Hydropower Sector Strategy for mainstreaming barrier removal within an NbS approach is being drafted, integrating the data from this RT3.
 - Key stakeholders, such as the IHA and Eurelectric, will be invited for bilateral discussions in the Autumn to explore if and how they may wish to support the further development of the ideas and actions outlined in the strategy.
 - Drawing the draft hydropower strategy process, alongside other economic sectors involved in MERLIN, an EU cross-sector routemap for mainstreaming an NbS approach for freshwater ecosystem restoration is also being developed.

For more information about this 3rd roundtable report or on other MERLIN project activities focused on mainstreaming NbS across economic sectors please contact esther.carmen@hutton.ac.uk